

THE SYSTEM AND DATA ANALYSIS PROGRAM IN LABVIEW

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Annotatsiya: *This article describes the LabVIEW program in practical applications on the basis of engineering in the field to be taught, shug as, bin which modern engineering procedures and scientific methods, high information technologyan using an out be carried, bher for educational laboratory and in demonstrasiya works with zero impact factor check by made and mathematical out be carried about thinking .*

Keywords: *information , communication, laboratory, manufacturing, integration, engineering, parameter, sensors, signal, analog, graphics palette.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada LabVIEW dasturidagi amaliy dasturlar asosida muhandislik sohasiga o'qitilishi, shuningdek, bunda zamonaviy muhandislik tartibotlari va ilmiy uslublarini o'rgatish, yuqori axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish amalga oshirilishi, buning uchun o'quv laboratoriya va demonstratsiya ishlari ko'p faktorli tekshirish orqali bajariladi va matematik modellashtirish amalga oshirilishi haqida fikr yuriltilgan.*

Kalit So'zlar: *axborot , kommunikatsiya, laboratoriya, texnologik, integratsiya, muhandislik, parameter, datchik, signal, analog, grafik palitralar*

ACCESS

Information and communication technologies for development in the modern world th e level of , in the republic world information space infrastructure and national information-computing network integration corresponding , which has a national system to create a national economy, management, science and education effective important factor to toe'are sought. These problems are much more complex and at the same time, our republic for pressing. Now out the new, structural and other to rise out to increase results in republic of the information with the garden'liq problem of how and which period the solution is to also be associated.

LabVIEW (laboratory a Vertual Instrumentation Engineering Workbench) — the national Instrument (Usa) firm by the “g” graphic programming language created program is. LabVIEW program on the firstversion currently its UNIX, GNU/linux, mac os versions are created. Especially his microsoft windows by created version is much more advanced and popular it is. LabVIEW data re - processing and system participatong work in, as well as the manufacturing facilities and processes in

management is used. LabVIEW scan the system very close bo'become, but it 's the difference technological processes automation and management systems (TJABT) within the issues are not, but automation of the system of scientific check (ATI) within the framework of the issues to address was. LabVIEWdasturida used "G" graphic programming language for data flow architecture based. Such programming in the language of operators, the sequence of performance in the order of (imperativ programming as such) is not, but available data, this operator entry by is determined. LabVIEW program on the basis vertual devices (Vertual the instrument) up makes. The program of the front panel, program management elements – buttons, graphics and other same as located bo'ladi.

In practice the year, such a step different physical and technological parameters including, movement speed, temperature, static and dynamic pressure, spend, satx , such as a time and continuous basis to require will. Such tasks of holding meetings in the performance of the main means of one LabVIEW graphical programming language is. LabVIEW program automation systems, construction, and experimental data for re - use in simple from the computer, pull - to high - level metrological characteristic information- to the system service makes. Laboratory device automation that is used for technical and software means of the platform in the first stage - this is the object, i.e. the physical value of the electrical signal instruments present particular laboratory of the device protected rga were the main focus. The second stage - the sensors analog signal to digital code to become commercial information of the council of coordinators automated boards, computer and to service consists. Also, the software module network also otherwise being a number of, their content, instruments and auxiliary devices of a drive consists. The third stage- the software environment, that is, automation, process data to, re - processing module creation and operation otherwise has held. Re - developments information rare cases useful info is stored will remain. In the beginning them to analysis for convenient to you need. Do this to noisy break moves out , remove, device error reduction and the impact needed.

Experience and quarters through the obtained information managing, for each a in laboratory work to the data to that may identify special programs is the creation of. This platform the stage is. Automated laboratory device turn with connection to a single computer by a out carried. to of the system to actual practice to, a time at 8 different parameters will and experience management 2 channel citizens out carried. Electrical signals and sensors, USB output with 12 discharge analog-digital is given. Data on the participationof job boards vine and voltage current value of 0.5 % up to accuracy in digital code to the will. Obtained digital signal LabVIEW program again will work. to the results of simple arrows or digital with , and devices in multimedia screen or computer monitor of the front panel are inserted. Direct experience at the time of the time - citizens parameters that representing graphics is built and they to each other to. Automation system design by means of electronic computing machines (EHM) is, the systemic approach and the capabilities of the development for the necessary basis as them managing other technical tools of creation. LabVIEW program

automation system design in a time electric of the device (frequency devices) functions perform enhancing, as well as, the results of re - work for special mathematical software functions, especially the authenticator requirements to provide the opportunity it gives. Physical object from the data to the same real - time mode as the information file in appointing result from the data obtained. Universal object- complex simplify and preparation of the possibility LabVIEW program out carried. Various of the functions and the results of re - work -digital and to the program suitable means out carries. Of these, the characteristic feature vertual devices is. The data in quarters of memory, the possibility to experience the results of in mind to keep, including covers analysis - check-in passengers , and the static again to work for the opportunity it gives.

LabVIEW program practical - software tools likes logical structure with high - level design language close. Usually the program in the creation of a wide range of users to the object the programming language to graphical programming language used.programming a universal system as LabVIEW program external devices with your work, re - work, and data ko'to rsat for wide comprehensive library has. LabVIEW at the program implementation increase vertual devices or vertual devices as using called, of them one how graphic showsthe real physical devices to use o'xshab to bo'present work the method and characteristic results are there. LabVIEW of the program, the front panel user interactive interface is, the program block-scheme of building a functional panel out carried. The block-scheme of the software to function graph be vavertual device start constipation in code performance reflect is held. Vertual device software out increasing his and the module work principles are used. Such as, LabVIEW program vailable options particular dasturosti in were expressed, as referred to the SubVI

LabVIEW palette. LabVIEW program in three graphic palette (Palette) - Tools palette the Tools Palette), control palette (the palette control), the function palette (the palette function) are there. They vertual devices create and out in increasing are used. Tools palette from the equipment is become, vertual device use and the construction for is. Tools pallet of activation of windows in the menu show the tools Palette, from the point it is called.

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